

“STUDYING THE MINERAL COMPOSITION OF RAPS SQUEEZE GROWN IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN”

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Abstract. *As the country's population grows, the need for protein products increases. It is necessary to provide the country's population with food products of increased biological and nutritional value. Various protein-containing additives introduced into food recipes play a huge role in this. One of the sources that increases the nutritional and biological value of food products is rapeseed squeeze.*

The purpose of the work was to study the amino mineral and mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The object of the study was squeezed from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan of the Viking variety. The amino mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze proteins was studied according to GOST 32195-2013 [1]. The mineral composition of rapeseed seed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan was determined using the atomic adsorption method on a solar atomic adsorption spectrometer. S 2. Squeeze from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan contains almost all essential amino minerals. Rapeseed seed squeeze contains a high content of leucine (2.28 g /100g), phenylamine (1.2 g /100g), isoleucine (1.03 g/ 100g), methionine (0.87 g/ 100g), tryptophan (0.431 g/ 100g). This indicates that the proteins in rapeseed squeeze have a complete amino mineral composition. The mineral composition of squeeze from rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized by a high content of P-1116%, magnesium-465%, calcium 232.5%, potassium-77.4%, zinc-9.38% and other macro and microelements. These research data indicate the advisability of using rapeseed squeeze in national dishes of Uzbekistan to increase nutritional and biological value.

Keywords. *rapeseed squeeze, protein, amino mineral composition, mineral composition, macro and microelements, amino mineral score, essential amino minerals, biological value.*

Annotatsiya. *Mamlakat aholisining ko'payishi bilan oqsilli mahsulotlarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Mamlakat aholisini biologik va ozuqaviy qiymati yuqori bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash zarur. Bunda oziq-ovqat retseptlariga kiritilgan turli xil proteinli qo'shimchalar katta rol o'ynaydi. Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining ozuqaviy va biologik qiymatini oshiradigan manbalardan biri raps siqmasidir.*

Ishning maqsadi O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps siqishining aminokislotalar va mineral tarkibini o'rganish edi. Tadqiqot ob'yekti O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan "Viking" navli raps urug'idan siqib chiqarildi. Raps siqish oqsillarining aminokislotalar tarkibi GOST 32195-2013 [4] bo'yicha o'rganilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'ining mineral tarkibi solar atom adsorbsion spektrometrida atom adsorbsion usuli yordamida aniqlandi. S 2. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'idan olingan siqish tarkibida deyarli barcha muhim aminokislotalar mavjud. Raps urug'i siqishida yuqori miqdorda leysin (2,28 g / 100 g), fenilamin (1,2 g / 100 g),

izolösin (1,03 g / 100 g), metionin (0,87 g / 100 g), triptofan (0,431 g / 100 g) mavjud. Bu raps siqishidagi oqsillarning to'liq aminokislota tarkibiga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps urug'idan siqishning mineral tarkibi P-1116%, magniy-465%, kaltsiy 232,5%, kaliy-77,4%, rux-9,38% va boshqa makro va mikroelementlarning yuqori miqdori bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu tadqiqot ma'lumotlari ozuqaviy va biologik qiymatini oshirish uchun O'zbekiston milliy taomlarida raps siqishidan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raps siqish, oqsil, aminokislotalar tarkibi, mineral tarkibi, makro va mikroelementlar, aminokislotalar reytingi, muhim aminokislotalar, biologik qiymati.

Аннотация. С ростом населения страны увеличивается потребность в белковых продуктах. Необходимо обеспечить население страны продуктами питания повышенной биологической и пищевой ценности. Огромную роль в этом играют различные белоксодержащие добавки, вводимые в рецептуры блюд. Одним из источников, повышающих пищевую и биологическую ценность продуктов питания, является рапсовый жом.

Целью работы было изучение минерального и минерального состава рапсового жома, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан. Объектом исследования являлся жом из семян рапса, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан сорта Викинг. Минеральный состав белков рапсового жома изучался по ГОСТ 32195-2013 [4]. Минеральный состав рапсового жома, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан, определялся с помощью атомно-адсорбционного метода на атомно-адсорбционном спектрометре solar. S 2. Жом из рапса, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан, содержит практически все незаменимые минералы. В выжимке из семян рапса обнаружено высокое содержание лейцина (2,28 г/100г), фениламина (1,2 г/100г), изолейцина (1,03 г/100г), метионина (0,87 г/100г), триптофана (0,431 г/100г). Это свидетельствует о том, что белки в выжимке из семян рапса имеют полноценный минеральный состав. Минеральный состав выжимки из семян рапса, выращенных в Республике Узбекистан, характеризуется высоким содержанием P-1116%, магния-465%, кальция 232,5%, калия-77,4%, цинка-9,38% и других макро- и микроэлементов. Полученные данные исследований свидетельствуют о целесообразности использования выжимки из семян рапса в национальных блюдах Узбекистана для повышения пищевой и биологической ценности.

Ключевые слова. Выжимка из семян рапса, белок, минеральный состав, минеральный состав, макро и микроэлементы, минеральный скор, незаменимые минералы, биологическая ценность.

Introduction

Currently, one of the priorities of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to provide the population with nutritious, high-protein food products. The average daily physiological requirement of a person for protein is constantly studied by the Ministry of Health of the Republic and is reflected in the decisions of the relevant mines and authorities. These indicators are indicative in nature, as they depend on the person's age, gender, nature of the work performed, physiological state, weather conditions, as well as environmental pollution. According to the indicative recommendations of WHO and FAO, the optimal protein requirement is 60-100 g per day or 12-15% of the total caloric intake. In the total amount of energy, protein of animal and plant origin accounts for 6-8% each. In terms of 1 kg of body

weight, the protein requirement per day for an adult is on average about 1 g, while for children, depending on age, it ranges from 1.05 to 4.00 g [2].

Recommended protein standards developed by the Russian scientific school of nutrition include 73-120 g of protein per day for men and 60-90 g for women. Here, the lower limit is recommended for people not involved in physical labor, and the upper limit for people engaged in heavy physical labor [3].

For an adult man, the required level of protein consumption in terms of nitrogen is 9.0-9.2 g per day per 1 kg of body weight, and for persons suffering severe infections, surgical interventions, and having digestive and respiratory diseases, it can increase to 110-120 g, and in diabetics, its amount can reach 130-140 g [4].

There is a shortage of dietary protein all over the world, including in our republic. Scientists are looking for new sources of protein that correspond to complete protein and contain all the essential amino minerals. One type of such raw material is rapeseed squeeze. Rapeseed is an oilseed crop and its cultivation solves the problem of providing vegetable oil, and the squeeze after obtaining the oil is a source of protein, vitamins, and minerals [4] .

The use of rapeseed squeeze as an additive to food products helps to increase the nutritional and biological value without increasing the cost of these products [5] .

Taking into account the above, we decided to study the amino mineral composition of protein and the content of minerals in the squeeze of rapeseed seeds grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan [6] .

The next stage of our research was to study the mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan .

The obtained data are shown in Table 1.

Content of macro and micro elements in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Table 1

Macro and micro elements, % of dry matter content	Content in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan	Contents in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Belarus
Aluminum	2.79	-
Calcium	232.5	1520.7
Sodium	3.72	-
Potassium	74.4	159.2
Iron	18.6	18.5
Magnesium	465	445.4
Phosphorus	1116	0.3
Bor	1.86	-
Manganese	3.72	11.3
Copper	0.465	-
Zinc	9.38	11.9

Data analysis table. 1. shows that in rapeseed varieties, Belarusian selection, the content of Ca and K is 1520.8 mg / 100 g and 1592.0 mg / 100 g, which exceeds the content of these elements in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan several times, because in our

samples, the content of these elements is respectively 232.5 mg / 100 g, and 74.4 mg / 100 g. In samples of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the P content is 1116 mg / 100 g. The P content in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan is several times higher than in samples of Belarusian rapeseed selection. In our opinion, such a high gap in this indicator is due to the conditions for growing rapeseed and climatic conditions. As you know, P is part of all tissues of the body. Phosphorus is involved in the synthesis and breakdown of substances in cells, regulates metabolism and is found in nucleic minerals. A deficiency of phosphorus in the diet leads to the fact that it will begin to use its own phosphorus - which leads to demineralization, disruption of structure - rarefaction. Considering the body's daily requirement of 1200 mg per day, administration as a food additive will help cover the body's phosphorus needs [7] . Rapeseed squeeze also has a high magnesium content Mg - 465 mg / 100g.

M g magnesium ensures the body's metabolism and maintains the normal function of the nervous system and heart muscles. It also dilates blood vessels, stimulates bile secretion, and improves intestinal motility [7].

Magnesium is poorly absorbed in the presence of phytin, excess fat, and is also a Ca antagonist.

Considering the daily requirement of magnesium is 200-300 mg/day , it should be introduced as an additive into national dishes. It will cover the body's entire need for this element.

As the data in Table 1 shows, rapeseed squeeze has a high content of C a. Ca is a structural component of bones and teeth. It is also part of cell nuclei, cellular and tissue fluids, and is involved in blood clotting. It is a difficult-to-digest element. Ca does not dissolve when entering the human body with food . In the alkaline environment of the small intestine, hard-to-digest Ca compounds are formed and when exposed to bile minerals, it is absorbed by the body. Also, calcium is poorly absorbed with a high content of Mg and P. Their recommended ratio according to sources is 1:0.5 and 1:1.5. As can be seen from the data in table. 1, the quantitative ratio meets the above requirements. Potassium is one of the vital intracellular elements that regulates the mineral-base balance in the blood. It reduces urine output, has protective properties against the unwanted effects of Na and normalizes blood pressure. Analyzing the data in Table 1, it can be noted that the introduction of rapeseed squeeze as an additive to the national dishes of Uzbekistan will help increase the nutritional and biological value without increasing the cost of these products, which is one of the key factors.

In our research work, we carried out a comparative analysis of the mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection [7]

Fig. 1. Comparative analysis of the content of macro and microelements of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection.

Analysis of the data in the figure shows that rapeseed squeeze obtained from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan is rich in minerals in its composition. Fluctuations in their content indicate their growing conditions and soil and climatic characteristics. There are no significant differences in the content of minerals grown in the two republics [8].

We also gave a comparative analysis between human needs and the content of minerals in rapeseed cake table. 2.

Table 2

The content of amino mineral substances in rapeseed cake and the daily human need for minerals

No.	Name mineral substances	Contents in rapeseed cake mg /100g	Daily requirement, for adults, mg
1.	Aluminum	279	8.6
2.	Calcium	232.5	800.0
3.	Sodium	3.72	400.0
4.	Potassium	74.4	2500
5.	Iron	18.6	14.0
6.	Magnesium	465	400.0
7.	Phosphorus	1116	1200.0
8.	Bor	1.86	1.5

9.	Manganese	3.72	1.8
10.	Honey	.0465	140
11.	Zinc	9.38	815.0

And analysis of the data from the table. Shows that rapeseed cake contains all the necessary minerals. The rapeseed cake contains all the necessary minerals for human life [9].

From the above studies, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Conclusions: Analysis of the amino mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze obtained from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that it contains all eight essential amino minerals. Rapeseed squeeze contains a high content of leucine - 3.66%, lysine - 2.99%, valine - 2.24%, isoleucine - 2.24%, threonine - 1.99%, as well as partially replaceable arginine - 3.44 %. This all indicates the high biological value of this raw material. The study also examined the mineral composition of rapeseed squeeze. Rapeseed squeeze is rich in minerals, and the high content of P, K, Ca, Mg Zn, Fe, Na and other elements shows that it can serve as a good source of food fortification and does not increase the cost of these dishes.

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